

A Preliminary Floristic Exploration in Thimmappakonda Sacred Grove, Anantapur District, Andhra Pradesh State

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Abstract

Background. Sacred groves in Andhra Pradesh are known as Pavithravanas. A total number of 730 sacred groves have been documented till date. These Pavithravanas or sacred groves are dedicated to various local deities and also to Hindu gods and goddesses. Some of the deities to whom the sacred groves are dedicated are Shiva, Rudrakoteswara, Hanuman, Saraswathi, Thimmaraya Swamy, Gangamma, Nagadevatha, Chennakesava, Narasimha and Akkamma (WWF Andhra Pradesh, 1996). **Results.** During study of sacred grove of Andhra Pradesh State, India various field trips were conducted and were GIS Photographic from various natural populations during the period 2013-2024. Collected Sacred groves identifications activities data and plants specimens collected flowering or fruiting seasons. Specimens critically observed and identified. In the present study, a total of 380 wild and naturalized species were recorded from Thimmappakonda Sacred grove, Anantapuramu District, Andhra Pradesh. These 380 wild and naturalized species belong to 242 genera and 63 families. Of the 380 wild and naturalized species, 42 trees, 54 shrubs; 246 herbs; 37 Climbers and remaining 1 species Liana. **Conclusion.** Sacred groves in Andhra Pradesh are deteriorating at an alarming rate due to changes in religious beliefs and developmental pressure. Many temples associated with sacred groves have been modernized by removing the vegetation. Some of the species commonly found in the sacred groves of Andhra Pradesh are black plum, tamarind, mango, jackfruit, neem, beechwood and pipal. Some of the species have unique abilities such as nitrogen fixation etc. Such Species are variously known as keystone species or functional groups.

Keywords: Pampanur, Pavithranams, Primary Data Collections, Sacred Grove.

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Introduction

The sacred groves are important repositories of floral and faunal diversity that have been conserved by local communities in a sustainable manner. They are often the last refuge of endemic species in the geographical region. The role of cultural and spiritual values is crucial to nature conservation. In India, the sacred groves are still in the process of being documented. There are 13,270 sacred groves that are found to intact (Murugesan, 2016). Out of this only 138 hectares comprise of totally undisturbed vegetation and about 3188 hectares have an open canopy. However, initial studies indicate that the number of sacred groves in the country may be as high as 100,000 to 150,000 (Malhotra, 1998; Murugesan, 2016). The total area under sacred groves in India has been estimated to be 33,000 hectares which comes to 0.01 percent of the total area of the country. However, the actual area could be as high as 42000 hectares considering the 4,445 sacred groves reported so far (Gokhale et al., 1998). However, in contrast to the above facts, C.P.R. Environmental Education Centre has so far documented a total of 10,377 sacred groves which have been authenticated (Murugesan, 2016). In India, over 1 million Sacred Forests and 100,000 to 150,000 sacred groves exist (IUCN, 2023). This spiritual belief is very similar to the mechanism of a healthy ecosystem.

Many scientists believe that traditions and faiths like these are essential to encourage biodiversity conservation efforts (Malhotra et al., 1998). A document of (MAB, 1995) has described the sacred groves present in Ghana, Senegal, and Sumatra (IUCN, 2023). Various sacred sites associated with rich vegetation in Bangladesh were reported by (Hussain, 1998). All forms of vegetation in the groves are supposed to be under the protection of reigning deity of that grove, and the removal of even a small twig is a taboo (Vartak and Gadgil, 1973). Collection and removal of any material from the sacred groves is prohibited (Khan et al., 1987; Khiewtam and Ramakrishnan, 1989). Sacred groves are found all over India especially in those regions where indigenous communities inhabit. Traced the historical link of sacred groves with the pre-agricultural, hunting and gathering stage, before human being had settled down to raise livestock or till land (Gadgil & Vartak, 1976; 1981a; 1981b). Most of the sacred groves reported from India are in the Western Ghats, North Eastern India and Central India (Gadgil & Vartak, 1976; Burman, 1992; Rodgers, 1994; Balasuramanyam & Induchoodan, 1996; Tripathi, 2006; Khumbongmayum et al., 2005). In India sacred groves are found mainly in tribal dominated areas and known by different names in ethnic terms (Bhakat, 1990) such as Sarna or Dev in Madhya Pradesh, Devrai or Deovani in Maharashtra, Sarnas in Bihar, Oran's in Rajasthan, Devaravana or Devarakadu in Karnataka, Sarpakavu and Kavuvu in Tamil Nadu and Kerala, Dev van in Himachal Pradesh, Law Lyngdoh or Law Kyntang etc. in Meghalaya, Sarana or Jaherthan in Jharkhand and Laiumang in Manipur (IUCN, 2023).

Materials and Methods

During study of sacred grove of Andhra Pradesh State, India various field trips were conducted and were vouched from various natural populations during the period 2013-2024. Collected Sacred groves identifications activities data and plants photographic data collected flowering or fruiting seasons. Plants critically observed and identified. Based on the information, plants were identified with the help of local floras and confirmed by comparing with authenticated specimens in Deccan

Regional Centre, BSI, Hyderabad, Coimbatore and central National herbarium (CAL), Calcutta. The state of Andhra Pradesh, alone, has over 500 sacred groves (Anon, 1996), Locally known as Pavithravanalu (Rao et al., 2001; Sunitha & Rao, 1999) studied the characteristics and distribution of the flora of the sacred groves in Kurnool district of Andhra Pradesh. (Prasad Varma et. al., 2023) reported a total of 67 species 57 genera and 32 families in Bodakondamma sacred grove, Eastern Ghats, Visakhapatnam District. Biodiversity of Sacred groves is preserved in mostly undisturbed condition probably due to certain taboos and religious beliefs (Lakshmi Narayana & Venkaiah, 1998). The Local people of each sacred grove in general also believe that their livelihood, security and cultural existence are complementary to the blessings of their deity (Prasad Varma, et al., 2023). Perusal of related published literature (Gamble, 1915; Gamble & Fischer, 1915; Gibbs, 1974; Halbar, 1986; Hooker ,1984; Hooker, 1872-1897; Jain, 1964; Jain & Rao, 1977; Jain, 1981; Jain, 1964; Jain, 1981; Kirtikar & Boser, 1933; Nadkarni, 1976; Pullaiah & Yasodamma, 1989; Pullaiah & Chennaiah, 1997; Rao & Sree Ramulu, 1986; Reddy et al., 1986; Subba Rao & Kumari, 2002-2008) for the taxonomic confirmation.

Atmakur village is located in Atmakur mandal of Anantapur District in Andhra Pradesh, India. The total geographical area of village is 5159 hectares. As per 2009 status, Pampanur is the gram panchayat of Atmakur village. Sri Vyasaraaju who was a spiritual teacher (Raja Guru) for Sri Krishna Deva Raya (1509 A.D- 1530 A.D), Installed Sri Subramanyeswara Swamy Idol here. Later, there is no much attention towards this temple. During 1980-90, this temple was renovated and started with daily poojas, In the year 2008, Sri Ganapathy Sachidhananda Swamy built the sub-temples for Lord Siva and Goddess Parvathi within the temple complex (GoTirupati, n.d.).

Results and Discussions

In the present study, a total of 380 wild and naturalized species were recorded from Thimmappakonda Scared grove, Anantapuramu District, Andhra Pradesh. These 380 wild and naturalized species belong to 242 genera and 63 families. Of the 380 wild and naturalized species, 42 trees, 54 shrubs; 246 herbs; 37 Climbers and remaining 1 species Liana. Sacred groves are ecologically, culturally, and spiritually significant. They serve as biodiversity hotspots, conserving rare and endemic species of flora and fauna. Ecologically, they act as carbon sinks, regulate microclimates, and prevent soil erosion. Culturally, they are integral to local traditions, often protected through religious beliefs, rituals, and taboos. They also support traditional knowledge systems, including medicinal plant usage. Despite their importance, sacred groves face threats like deforestation and urbanization, highlighting the need for conservation efforts that integrate local communities and modern ecological strategies. Floristic exploration of sacred groves is a vital activity for understanding and conserving plant biodiversity.

Conclusion

Sacred groves are unique ecosystems, often serving as reservoirs of rare, endemic, and medicinal plant species. Here are the key reasons why floristic exploration is crucial. Sacred groves are biodiversity hotspots. Floristic exploration helps identify and catalogue plant species, including those that are rare, endangered, or have limited geographical distribution. Trees and plants in sacred groves play a significant role in carbon capture. Identifying dominant species helps estimate their carbon storage potential. Plants in sacred groves often exhibit resilience to climate extremes. Exploring their floristic composition can provide insights into climate-adaptive species. Floristic surveys can reveal the impact of deforestation, grazing, and urbanization on plant diversity, emphasizing the need for conservation. Identifying invasive plant species helps manage threats to

native flora. Floristic exploration in sacred groves is not just a scientific endeavour but also a conservation imperative. It integrates traditional knowledge with modern science, ensuring that these ancient ecological sanctuaries continue to thrive and provide their invaluable benefits to nature and society.

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Appendixes

Table 1. Plant Species Check List- Provided A-Z Families wise

S.No	Families	Name of the Species	Habit
1	Acanthaceae	<i>Andrographis serpyllifolia</i> (Rottl. ex Vahl.) Wt.	H
2	Acanthaceae	<i>Andrographis paniculata</i> (Burm.f.) Nees	H
3	Acanthaceae	<i>Barleria cristata</i> L.	S
4	Acanthaceae	<i>Andrographis echioides</i> (L.) Nees	H
5	Acanthaceae	<i>Barleria noctiflora</i> L.f.	S
6	Acanthaceae	<i>Barleria prionitis</i> L.	S
7	Acanthaceae	<i>Blepharis integrifolia</i> (L.f.) E.Mey. & Drège ex Schinz	H
8	Acanthaceae	<i>Blepharis maderaspatensis</i> (L.) B.Heyne ex Roth	H
9	Acanthaceae	<i>Dicliptera paniculata</i> (Forssk.) I.Darbysh	H
10	Acanthaceae	<i>Dipteracanthus prostratus</i> (Poir.) Nees	H
11	Acanthaceae	<i>Ecbolium viride</i> (Forssk.) Alston	H
12	Acanthaceae	<i>Elytraria acaulis</i> (L.f.) Lindau	H
13	Acanthaceae	<i>Hygrophila auriculata</i> (Schumach.) Heine	H
14	Acanthaceae	<i>Justicia glauca</i> Rottler	H
15	Acanthaceae	<i>Justicia procumbens</i> L.	H
16	Acanthaceae	<i>Lepidagathis cristata</i> Willd.	H
17	Acanthaceae	<i>Rostellularia prostrata</i> (C.B.Clarke) R.B.Majumdar	H
18	Acanthaceae	<i>Ruellia patula</i> Jacq	H
19	Acanthaceae	<i>Rungia pectinata</i> (L.) Nees	H
20	Acanthaceae	<i>Rungia repens</i> (L.) Nees	H
21	Aizoaceae	<i>Trianthema portulacastrum</i> L.	H
22	Aizoaceae	<i>Trianthema triquetra</i> Rottler & Willd.	H
23	Aizoaceae	<i>Zaleya decandra</i> (L.) Burm.f.	H
24	Amaranthaceae	<i>Achyranthes aspera</i> L.	H
25	Amaranthaceae	<i>Aerva javanica</i> (Burm.f.) Juss. ex Schult.	H
26	Amaranthaceae	<i>Aerva lanata</i> (L.) Juss.	H
27	Amaranthaceae	<i>Allmania nodiflora</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Wight	H
28	Amaranthaceae	<i>Alternanthera pungens</i> Kunth	H
29	Amaranthaceae	<i>Alternanthera sessilis</i> (L.) R.Br. ex DC.	H
30	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus spinosus</i> L.	H
31	Amaranthaceae	<i>Amaranthus viridis</i> L.	H
32	Amaranthaceae	<i>Celosia argentea</i> L.	H
33	Amaranthaceae	<i>Digera muricata</i> (L.) Mart.	H

34	Amaranthaceae	<i>Gomphrena serrata</i> L.	H
35	Amaranthaceae	<i>Pupalia lappacea</i> (L.) Juss.	H
36	Amaranthaceae	<i>Trichuriella monsoniae</i> (L. f.) Bennet	H
37	Anacardiaceae	<i>Searsia mysorensis</i> (G.Don) Moffett	T
38	Annonaceae	<i>Annona squamosa</i> L.	T
39	Apocyanaceae	<i>Calotropis gigantea</i> (L.) Dryand.	S
40	Apocyanaceae	<i>Calotropis procera</i> (Aiton) Dryand.	S
41	Apocyanaceae	<i>Caralluma adscendens</i> (Roxb.) R.Br.	H
42	Apocynaceae	<i>Caralluma umbellata</i> Haw.	H
43	Apocyanaceae	<i>Carissa carandas</i> L.	S
44	Apocyanaceae	<i>Catharanthus pusillus</i> (Murray) G.Don	H
45	Apocyanaceae	<i>Cryptostegia grandiflora</i> Roxb. ex R.Br.	C
46	Apocyanaceae	<i>Dregea volubilis</i> (L.f.) Benth. ex Hook.f.	C
47	Apocyanaceae	<i>Gymnema sylvestre</i> (Retz.) R.Br. ex Sm.	C
48	Apocyanaceae	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) R. Br. ex Schult.	H
49	Apocyanaceae	<i>Leptadenia reticulata</i> (Retz.) Wight & Arn	C
50	Apocyanaceae	<i>Oxystelma esculentum</i> (L. f.) Sm.	L
51	Apocyanaceae	<i>Pentatropis capensis</i> (L. f.) Bullock	Twin
52	Apocyanaceae	<i>Pergularia daemia</i> (Forssk.) Chiov.	C
53	Apocyanaceae	<i>Sarcostemma acidum</i> (Roxb.) Voigt	Twin
54	Apocyanaceae	<i>Wrightia tinctoria</i> R.Br.	T
55	Arecaceae	<i>Phoenix sylvestris</i> (L.) Roxb	T
56	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia bracteata</i>	H
57	Aristolochiaceae	<i>Aristolochia indica</i> L.	Twin
58	Asparagaceae	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd.	C
59	Asparagaceae	<i>Drimia indica</i> (Roxb.) Jessop	H
60	Asparagaceae	<i>Ledebouria revoluta</i> (L.f.) Jessop	H
61	Asteraceae	<i>Acanthospermum hispidum</i> DC	H
62	Asteraceae	<i>Blainvillea acmella</i> (L.) Philipson	H
63	Asteraceae	<i>Blumea bifoliata</i> (L.) DC	H
64	Asteraceae	<i>Blumea eriantha</i> DC	H
65	Asteraceae	<i>Blumea obliqua</i> (L.) Druce	H
66	Asteraceae	<i>Cyanthillium cinereum</i> (L.) H.Rob	H
67	Asteraceae	<i>Dicoma tomentosa</i> Cass.	H
68	Asteraceae	<i>Echinops echinatus</i> Roxb	H
69	Asteraceae	<i>Eclipta prostrata</i> (L.) L.	H
70	Asteraceae	<i>Emilia sonchifolia</i> (L.) DC. ex DC.	H
71	Asteraceae	<i>Glossocardia bosvallia</i> (L.f.) DC	H
72	Asteraceae	<i>Lagascea mollis</i> Cav.	H
73	Asteraceae	<i>Parthenium hysterophorus</i> L.	H
74	Asteraceae	<i>Pentanema indicum</i> (L.) Ling	H
75	Asteraceae	<i>Pulicaria wightiana</i> (DC.) C.B.Clarke	H
76	Asteraceae	<i>Sphaeranthus indicus</i> L.	H
77	Asteraceae	<i>Tridax procumbens</i> (L.) L.	H

78	Asteraceae	<i>Xanthium strumarium</i> L.	S
79	Bignoniaceae	<i>Dolichandrone falcata</i> (Wall. ex DC.) Seem	T
80	Bignoniaceae	<i>Tecoma stans</i> (L.) Juss. ex Kunth	S
81	Boraginaceae	<i>Coldenia procumbens</i> L.	H
82	Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium bracteatum</i> R.Br.	H
83	Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium indicum</i> L.	H
84	Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium strigosum</i> Willd.	H
85	Boraginaceae	<i>Heliotropium zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) Lam.	H
86	Boraginaceae	<i>Rotula aquatica</i> Lour.	H
87	Boraginaceae	<i>Trichodesma indicum</i> (L.) Lehm.	H
88	Boraginaceae	<i>Trichodesma zeylanicum</i> (Burm.f.) R.Br	H
89	Cactaceae	<i>Opuntia stricta</i> (Haw.) Haw.	S
90	Capparaceae	<i>Cadaba fruticosa</i> (L.) Druce	S
91	Capparaceae	<i>Capparis decidua</i> (Forssk.) Edgew	S
92	Capparaceae	<i>Capparis divaricata</i> Lam	T
93	Capparaceae	<i>Capparis floribunda</i> Lepr. ex Walp	S
94	Capparaceae	<i>Maerua oblongifolia</i> (Forssk.) A.Rich	S
95	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Polycarpaea aurea</i> Wight & Arn.	H
96	Caryophyllaceae	<i>Polycarpaea corymbosa</i> (L.) Lam	H
97	Celastraceae	<i>Gymnosporia emarginata</i> (Willd.) Thwaites	S
98	Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome aspera</i> J.Koenig ex DC.	H
99	Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome gynandra</i> L.	H
100	Cleomaceae	<i>Cleome viscosa</i> L.	H
101	Combretaceae	<i>Anogeissus latifolia</i> (Roxb. ex DC.) Wall. ex Guillem. & Perr.	T
102	Combretaceae	<i>Combretum albidum</i> G.Don	S
103	Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina attenuata</i> K.D.Koenig ex Vahl	H
104	Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina benghalensis</i> L.	H
105	Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina clavata</i> C.B.Clarke	H
106	Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina diffusa</i> Burm.f.	H
107	Commelinaceae	<i>Commelina ensifolia</i> R.Br.	H
108	Commelinaceae	<i>Cyanotis axillaris</i> (L.) D.Don ex Sweet	H
109	Commelinaceae	<i>Cyanotis fasciculata</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Schult. & Schult.f.	H
110	Commelinaceae	<i>Cyanotis tuberosa</i> (Roxb.) Schult. & Schult.f.	H
111	Commelinaceae	<i>Murdannia spirata</i> (L.) G.Brückn.	H
112	Convolvulaceae	<i>Cuscuta chinensis</i> Lam.	C
113	Convolvulaceae	<i>Evolvulus alsinoides</i> (L.) L.	H
114	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea hederifolia</i> L.	C
115	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea obscura</i> (L.) Ker Gawl.	C
116	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea pes-tigridis</i> L.	C
117	Convolvulaceae	<i>Ipomoea staphylina</i> Roem. & Schult.	C
118	Convolvulaceae	<i>Merremia aegyptia</i> (L.) Urb	C
119	Convolvulaceae	<i>Merremia gangetica</i> Cufod.	C

120	Convolvulaceae	<i>Merremia tridentata</i> (L.) Hallier f.	C
121	Cornaceae	<i>Alangium salviifolium</i> (L.f.) Wangerin	S
122	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Coccinia grandis</i> (L.) Voigt	C
123	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Corallocarpus epigaeus</i> (Rottler) Hook.f.	C
124	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Ctenolepis garcini</i> (L.) C.B.Clarke	C
125	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Diplocyclos palmatus</i> (L.) C.Jeffrey	C
126	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Kedrostis foetidissima</i> (Jacq.) Cogn.	C
127	Cucurbitaceae	<i>Mukia maderaspatana</i> (L.) M.Roem.	C
128	Cyperaceae	<i>Bulbostylis barbata</i> (Rottb.) C.B.Clarke	C
129	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus iria</i> L.	H
130	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus laevigatus</i> L.	H
131	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus nutans</i> Vahl	H
132	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus rotundus</i> L.	H
133	Cyperaceae	<i>Cyperus rubicundus</i> Vahl	H
134	Cyperaceae	<i>Eleocharis atropurpurea</i> (Retz.) J.Presl & C.Presl	H
135	Cyperaceae	<i>Fimbristylis cymosa</i> R.Br.	H
136	Cyperaceae	<i>Fimbristylis dichotoma</i> (L.) Vahl	H
137	Cyperaceae	<i>Kyllinga bulbosa</i> P.Beauv.	H
138	Cyperaceae	<i>Kyllinga nemoralis</i> (J.R.Forst. & G.Forst.) Dandy ex Hutch. & Dalziel	H
139	Cyperaceae	<i>Pycnus flavidus</i> (Retz.) T.Koyama	H
140	Elatinaceae	<i>Bergia ammannioides</i> Roxb. ex Roth	H
141	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha alnifolia</i> Klein ex Willd.	S
142	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha indica</i> L.	H
143	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha lanceolata</i> Willd.	H
144	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Acalypha malabarica</i> Müll.Arg	H
145	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Chrozophora rottleri</i> (Geiseler) A.Juss. ex Spreng	H
146	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Croton bonplandianus</i> Baill.	H
147	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia antiquorum</i> L.	T
148	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia heterophylla</i> L.	H
149	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L.	H
150	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Euphorbia indica</i> Lam.	H
151	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Jatropha gossypifolia</i> L.	S
152	Euphorbiaceae	<i>Micrococca mercurialis</i> (L.) Benth	H
153	Fabaceae	<i>Abrus precatorius</i> L	C
154	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia auriculiformis</i> Benth	T
155	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia caesia</i> (L.) Willd.	S
156	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia catechu</i> (L.f.) Willd.	T
157	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia chundra</i> (Rottler) Willd	T
158	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia farnesiana</i> (L.) Willd.	T
159	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia ferruginea</i> DC	T
160	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia horrida</i> (L.) Willd.	T
161	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia leucophloea</i> (Roxb.) Willd.	T

162	Fabaceae	<i>Acacia torta</i> (Roxb.) Craib	S
163	Fabaceae	<i>Aeschynomene indica</i> L	H
164	Fabaceae	<i>Albizia amara</i> (Roxb.) B.Boivin	T
165	Fabaceae	<i>Alysicarpus hamosus</i> Edgew.	H
166	Fabaceae	<i>Alysicarpus heterophyllus</i> (Baker) Jafri & Ali	H
167	Fabaceae	<i>Alysicarpus monilifer</i> (L.) DC	H
168	Fabaceae	<i>Alysicarpus vaginalis</i> (L.) DC	H
169	Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia purpurea</i> L.	T
170	Fabaceae	<i>Bauhinia racemosa</i> Lam.	T
171	Fabaceae	<i>Cassia fistula</i> L.	T
172	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista absus</i> (L.) H.S.Irwin & Barneby	H
173	Fabaceae	<i>Chamaecrista pumila</i> (Lam.) K.Larsen	H
174	Fabaceae	<i>Clitoria ternatea</i> L	C
175	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria angulata</i> Mill	H
176	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria hebecarpa</i> (DC.) Rudd	H
177	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria juncea</i> L	H
178	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria medicaginea</i> Lam	H
179	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria ramosissima</i> Roxb	H
180	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria retusa</i> L	H
181	Fabaceae	<i>Crotalaria verrucosa</i> L.	H
182	Fabaceae	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i> DC.	T
183	Fabaceae	<i>Desmodium gangeticum</i> (L.) DC.	H
184	Fabaceae	<i>Desmodium triflorum</i> (L.) DC.	H
185	Fabaceae	<i>Dichrostachys cinerea</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	S
186	Fabaceae	<i>Galactia tenuiflora</i> (Willd.) Wight & Arn.	C
187	Fabaceae	<i>Hardwickia binata</i> Roxb	T
188	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera hirsuta</i> L.	S
189	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera linifolia</i> (L.f.) Retz.	H
190	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera linnaei</i> Ali	H
191	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera prostrata</i> Willd.	H
192	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera tinctoria</i> L.	S
193	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera trifoliata</i> L.	S
194	Fabaceae	<i>Indigofera trita</i> L.f.	S
195	Fabaceae	<i>Mimosa hamata</i> Willd	S
196	Fabaceae	<i>Mimosa pudica</i> L.	H
197	Fabaceae	<i>Pithecellobium dulce</i> (Roxb.) Benth	T
198	Fabaceae	<i>Pongamia pinnata</i> (L.) Pierre	T
199	Fabaceae	<i>Prosopis chilensis</i> (Molina) Stuntz	T
200	Fabaceae	<i>Prosopis cineraria</i> (L.) Druce	T
201	Fabaceae	<i>Pseudarthria viscida</i> (L.) Wight & Arn	H
202	Fabaceae	<i>Pterolobium hexapetalum</i> (Roth) Santapau & Wagh	S
203	Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia capitata</i> (Roth) DC	C
204	Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia minima</i> (L.) DC.	H

205	Fabaceae	<i>Rhynchosia suaveolens</i> (L.f.) DC	S
206	Fabaceae	<i>Senna auriculata</i> (L.) Roxb	S
207	Fabaceae	<i>Senna italica</i> Mill	H
208	Fabaceae	<i>Senna occidentalis</i> (L.) Link	S
209	Fabaceae	<i>Senna tora</i> (L.) Roxb	H
210	Fabaceae	<i>Sesbania bispinosa</i> (Jacq.) W.Wight	S
211	Fabaceae	<i>Stylosanthes fruticosa</i> (Retz.) Alston	H
212	Fabaceae	<i>Tamarindus indica</i> L	T
213	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia maxima</i> (L.) Pers	H
214	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia pumila</i> (Lam.) Pers.	H
215	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia purpurea</i> (L.) Pers.	H
216	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia strigosa</i> (Dalzell) Santapau & Maheshw.	H
217	Fabaceae	<i>Tephrosia villosa</i> (L.) Pers.	H
218	Fabaceae	<i>Vigna aconitifolia</i> (Jacq.) Marechal	H
219	Fabaceae	<i>Vigna trilobata</i> (L.) Verdc.	H
220	Fabaceae	<i>Zornia gibbosa</i> Span.	H
221	Gentianaceae	<i>Enicostema axillare</i> (Poir. ex Lam.) A.Raynal	H
222	Gisekiaceae	<i>Gisekia pharnaceoides</i> L.	H
223	Hernandiaceae	<i>Gyrocarpus americanus</i> Jacq.	T
224	Lamiaceae	<i>Anisomeles malabarica</i> (L.) R.Br. ex Sims	H
225	Lamiaceae	<i>Gmelina asiatica</i> L.	T
226	Lamiaceae	<i>Hyptis suaveolens</i> (L.) Poit	H
227	Lamiaceae	<i>Leonotis nepetifolia</i> (L.) R.Br.	H
228	Lamiaceae	<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link	H
229	Lamiaceae	<i>Leucas diffusa</i> Benth	H
230	Lamiaceae	<i>Ocimum americanum</i> L.	H
231	Lamiaceae	<i>Ocimum gratissimum</i> L.	H
232	Lamiaceae	<i>Orthosiphon rubicundus</i> (D.Don) Benth.	H
233	Lauraceae	<i>Cassytha filiformis</i> L.	C
234	Loganiaceae	<i>Strychnos nux-vomica</i> L.	T
235	Loganiaceae	<i>Strychnos potatorum</i> L.f.	T
236	Lophiocarpaceae	<i>Corbichonia decumbens</i> (Forssk.) Exell	H
237	Loranthaceae	<i>Dendrophthoe falcata</i> (L.f.) Ettingsh.	S
238	Lythraceae	<i>Ammannia baccifera</i> L.	H
239	Malvaceae	<i>Abelmoschus ficulneus</i> (L.) Wight & Arn.	H
240	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon hirtum</i> (Lam.) Sweet	S
241	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon indicum</i> (L.) Sweet	S
242	Malvaceae	<i>Abutilon pannosum</i> (G.Forst.) Schltldl	S
243	Malvaceae	<i>Corchorus aestuans</i> L	H
244	Malvaceae	<i>Corchorus fascicularis</i> Lam	S
245	Malvaceae	<i>Corchorus trilocularis</i> L	H
246	Malvaceae	<i>Corchorus urticifolius</i> Wight & Arn.	H

247	Malvaceae	<i>Grewia hirsuta</i> Vahl	S
248	Malvaceae	<i>Grewia tenax</i> (Forssk.) Fiori	S
249	Malvaceae	<i>Grewia villosa</i> Willd	S
250	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus lobatus</i> (Murray) Kuntze	S
251	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus micranthus</i> L.f.	H
252	Malvaceae	<i>Hibiscus vitifolius</i> L.	S
253	Malvaceae	<i>Malvastrum coromandelianum</i> (L.) Garcke	H
254	Malvaceae	<i>Melhania incana</i> B.Heyne ex Wall.	H
255	Malvaceae	<i>Melochia corchorifolia</i> L.	H
256	Malvaceae	<i>Pavonia odorata</i> Willd	S
257	Malvaceae	<i>Pavonia zeylanica</i> (L.) Cav	H
258	Malvaceae	<i>Sida acuta</i> Burm.f.	H
259	Malvaceae	<i>Sida cordata</i> (Burm.f.) Borss.Waalk	H
260	Malvaceae	<i>Sida cordifolia</i> L.	H
261	Malvaceae	<i>Sida spinosa</i> L.	H
262	Malvaceae	<i>Triumfetta pentandra</i> A.Rich	H
263	Malvaceae	<i>Triumfetta rhomboidea</i> Jacq	H
264	Malvaceae	<i>Urena lobata</i> L.	H
265	Malvaceae	<i>Waltheria indica</i> L.	S
266	Martyniaceae	<i>Martynia annua</i> L.	H
267	Meliaceae	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> A.Juss	T
268	Menispermaceae	<i>Cissampelos pareira</i> L.	V
269	Menispermaceae	<i>Cocculus hirsutus</i> (L.) W.Theob.	C
270	Menispermaceae	<i>Tinospora sinensis</i> (Lour.) Merr. (= <i>T. cordifolia</i> (Willd.) Miers)	V
271	Molluginaceae	<i>Glinus lotoides</i> L.	H
272	Molluginaceae	<i>Glinus oppositifolius</i> (L.) Aug.DC.	H
273	Molluginaceae	<i>Mollugo nudicaulis</i> Lam	H
274	Molluginaceae	<i>Mollugo pentaphylla</i> L.	H
275	Moraceae	<i>Ficus benghalensis</i> L.	T
276	Moraceae	<i>Ficus racemosa</i> L.	T
277	Moraceae	<i>Ficus religiosa</i> L.	T
278	Nyctaginaceae	<i>Boerhavia chinensis</i> (L.) Rottb	H
279	Nyctaginaceae	<i>Boerhavia diffusa</i> L.	H
280	Nyctaginaceae	<i>Boerhavia erecta</i> L.	H
281	Oleaceae	<i>Jasminum auriculatum</i> Vahl	S
282	Orobanchaceae	<i>Striga angustifolia</i> (D. Don) C.J. Saldanha	H
283	Orobanchaceae	<i>Striga asiatica</i> (L.) Kuntze	H
284	Papaveraceae	<i>Argemone mexicana</i> L.	H
285	Passifloraceae	<i>Passiflora foetida</i> L.	V
286	Pedaliaceae	<i>Pedaliium murex</i> L.	H
287	Pedaliaceae	<i>Sesamum alatum</i> Thonn	H
288	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Flueggea leucopyrus</i> Willd.	S

289	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Phyllanthus amarus</i> Schumach. & Thonn.	H
290	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Phyllanthus debilis</i> Klein ex Willd.	H
291	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i> L.	T
292	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Phyllanthus maderaspatensis</i> L.	H
293	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Phyllanthus reticulatus</i> Poir.	S
294	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Phyllanthus virgatus</i> G.Forst.	H
295	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Tragia involucrata</i> L.	H
296	Phyllanthaceae	<i>Tragia plukenetii</i> Radcl.-Sm	H
297	Plantaginaceae	<i>Bacopa monnieri</i> (L.) Wettst.	H
298	Plumbaginaceae	<i>Plumbago zeylanica</i> L.	H
299	Poaceae	<i>Acrachne racemosa</i> (B.Heyne ex Roth) Ohwi	H
300	Poaceae	<i>Alloteropsis cimicina</i> (L.) Stapf	H
301	Poaceae	<i>Apluda mutica</i> L.	H
302	Poaceae	<i>Aristida adscensionis</i> L.	H
303	Poaceae	<i>Aristida setacea</i> Retz.	H
304	Poaceae	<i>Bothriochloa pertusa</i> (L.) A.Camus	H
305	Poaceae	<i>Brachiaria distachya</i> (L.) Stapf	H
306	Poaceae	<i>Brachiaria mutica</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	H
307	Poaceae	<i>Brachiaria ramosa</i> (L.) Stapf	H
308	Poaceae	<i>Brachiaria reptans</i> (L.) C.A.Gardner & C.E.Hubb.	H
309	Poaceae	<i>Cenchrus ciliaris</i> L.	H
310	Poaceae	<i>Chloris barbata</i> Sw.	H
311	Poaceae	<i>Chrysopogon fulvus</i> (Spreng.) Chiov.	H
312	Poaceae	<i>Cymbopogon caesius</i> (Hook. & Arn.) Stapf	H
313	Poaceae	<i>Cymbopogon coloratus</i> (Hook.f.) Stapf	H
314	Poaceae	<i>Cynodon dactylon</i> (L.) Pers.	H
315	Poaceae	<i>Dactyloctenium aegyptium</i> (L.) Willd	H
316	Poaceae	<i>Dichanthium annulatum</i> (Forssk.) Stapf	H
317	Poaceae	<i>Digitaria bicornis</i> (Lam.) Roem. & Schult.	H
318	Poaceae	<i>Digitaria ciliaris</i> (Retz.) Koeler	H
319	Poaceae	<i>Digitaria tomentosa</i> (J.Koenig ex Rottler) Henrard	H
320	Poaceae	<i>Dinebra retroflexa</i> (Vahl) Panz.	H
321	Poaceae	<i>Echinochloa colona</i> (L.) Link	H
322	Poaceae	<i>Eleusine indica</i> (L.) Gaertn.	H
323	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostiella bifaria</i> (Vahl) Bor	H
324	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostiella brachyphylla</i> (Stapf) Bor	H
325	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostis amabilis</i> (L.) Wight & Arn	H
326	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostis atrovirens</i> (Desf.) Trin. ex Steud.	H
327	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostis japonica</i> (Thunb.) Trin	H
328	Poaceae	<i>Eragrostis viscosa</i> (Retz.) Trin.	H
329	Poaceae	<i>Eriochloa procera</i> (Retz.) C.E.Hubb.	H
330	Poaceae	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> (L.) P.Beauv. ex Roem. & Schult.	H
331	Poaceae	<i>Iseilema laxum</i> Hack.	H
332	Poaceae	<i>Melanocenthris jacquemontii</i> Jaub. & Spach	H

333	Poaceae	<i>Oplismenus burmanni</i> (Retz.) P. Beauv	H
334	Poaceae	<i>Panicum repens</i> L.	H
335	Poaceae	<i>Paspalum distichum</i> L.	H
336	Poaceae	<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	H
337	Poaceae	<i>Perotis indica</i> (L.) Kuntze	H
338	Poaceae	<i>Setaria intermedia</i> Roem. & Schult.	H
339	Poaceae	<i>Setaria pumila</i> (Poir.) Roem. & Schult.	H
340	Poaceae	<i>Setaria verticillata</i> (L.) P. Beauv.	H
341	Poaceae	<i>Sporobolus coromandelianus</i> (Retz.) Kunth	H
342	Poaceae	<i>Tetrapogon tenellus</i> (Roxb.) Chiov	H
343	Poaceae	<i>Urochloa panicoides</i> P. Beauv.	H
344	Polygalaceae	<i>Polygala arvensis</i> Willd.	H
345	Polygalaceae	<i>Polygala chinensis</i> L.	H
346	Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca oleracea</i> L.	H
347	Portulacaceae	<i>Portulaca quadrifida</i> L.	H
348	Rhamnaceae	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i> Lam.	T
349	Rhamnaceae	<i>Ziziphus oenopolia</i> (L.) Mill	S
350	Rhamnaceae	<i>Ziziphus xylopyrus</i> (Retz.) Willd.	T
351	Rubiaceae	<i>Benkara malabarica</i> (Lam.) Tirveng	S
352	Rubiaceae	<i>Catunaregam spinosa</i> (Thunb.) Tirveng.	S
353	Rubiaceae	<i>Kohautia aspera</i> (B. Heyne ex Roth) Bremek	H
354	Rubiaceae	<i>Morinda pubescens</i> Sm.	T
355	Rubiaceae	<i>Oldenlandia corymbosa</i> L.	H
356	Rubiaceae	<i>Oldenlandia herbacea</i> (L.) Roxb	H
357	Rubiaceae	<i>Oldenlandia umbellata</i> L.	H
358	Rubiaceae	<i>Spermacoce articularis</i> L.f.	H
359	Rubiaceae	<i>Spermacoce pusilla</i> Wall.	H
360	Rutaceae	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> (L.) Corrêa	T
361	Rutaceae	<i>Chloroxylon swietenia</i> DC.	T
362	Sapindaceae	<i>Cardiospermum corundum</i> L.	C
363	Sapindaceae	<i>Cardiospermum halicacabum</i> L.	C
364	Sapindaceae	<i>Dodonaea viscosa</i> (L.) Jacq.	S
365	Sapindaceae	<i>Sapindus emarginatus</i> Vahl	T
366	Solanaceae	<i>Datura innoxia</i> Mill.	S
367	Solanaceae	<i>Physalis minima</i> L.	H
368	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum anguivi</i> Lam	S
369	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum incanum</i> L.	S
370	Solanaceae	<i>Solanum surattense</i> Burm. f.	H
371	Solanaceae	<i>Withania somnifera</i> (L.) Dunal	H
372	Typhaceae	<i>Typha angustifolia</i> L.	H
373	Verbenaceae	<i>Lantana camara</i> L.	S
374	Verbenaceae	<i>Phyla nodiflora</i> (L.) Greene	H

375	Verbenaceae	<i>Stachytarpheta jamaicensis</i> (L.) Vahl	H
376	Violaceae	<i>Pigea enneasperma</i> (L.) P.I. Forst. (= <i>Hybanthus enneaspermus</i> (L.) F.Muell.)	H
377	Vitaceae	<i>Cissus quadrangularis</i> L.	Vine
378	Vitaceae	<i>Cyphostemma setosum</i> (Roxb.) Alston	C
379	Zygophyllaceae	<i>Tribulus terrestris</i> L.	H
380	Zygophyllaceae	<i>Balanites aegyptiaca</i> (L.) Delile	T

Note: T Tree. S Shrub. C Climber. V Vine. H Herb.

A

B

C

D

Figure 1. A - Front View of Lakshminarasimha Swamy Temple. B - Showing Vegetations (GIS Image). C - Sri Mahalakshmi Temple. D - Showing Hill Top Rocky Area

Abelmoschus ficulneus

Abrus precatorius

Abutilon hirtum

Acacia catechu

Acacia horrida

Albizia amara

Figure 2. Plant Species Images

Anisomeles malabarica

Benkara malabarica

Blepharis maderaspatensis

Carissa carandas

Cassia fistula

Catunaregam spinosa

Figure 3. Plant Species Images

Crotalaria ramosissima

Euphorbia antiquorum

Kedrostis foetidissima

Lagascea mollis

Maerua oblongifolia

Opuntia stricta

Figure 4. Plant Species Images

